

Psychological Effects of Cyber Bullying on College Students: Indian Perspective

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Abstract: The research work identifies various psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India. The other objectives were to find the relationship between demographic aspects and psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents and to compare traditional bullying and cyber bullying impact on psychosocial behaviour in Indian perspective. Accordingly, the survey method was being used in which primary data was collected using well-structured questionnaire. A survey of 500 students revealed that 80% had experienced cyberbullying. The instrument was tested for reliability and validity using “Cronbach's Alpha Method” and the results suggested that as the calculated value of Cronbach's Alpha was 0.91 which shows high internal consistency in the scale being used. Research design includes sample size of 500 respondents selected from various colleges of India using the convenience sampling technique. The most prevalent psychological impacts were increased frustration (92%), anger (90%), and anxiety (90%). Statistical analysis found significant associations between these consequences and demographic factors such as gender and age. It can be concluded that cyber bullying has very high impact on psychological behaviour of college going students. Recommendations include implementing awareness programs, providing campus counselling services, and integrating digital literacy into curricula to mitigate the negative effects.

Keywords: Cyber Bullying, Traditional Bullying, Psychological Consequences, India, College Students

1. Introduction:

Cyber bullying is victimization includes posting, sending, sharing wrong negative information, mean content about an individual it also includes sharing private and personal information about someone through digital gadgets like desktops, tablets, cell phones, smart phones, laptops etc. which causes distress, frustration and humiliation or embarrassment to the cyber bullying victim (Maurya et al., 2022). The ways in which cyber bullying incident occur includes SMS, mobile applications, community, forums, gaming platform, blogs, online appearances, sharing the content, social media websites etc. Mainly the research paper focuses on identifying the psychological consequences due to cyber bullying incidents on college going students (Sandhu and Kaur, 2022). This study aims to address this gap by identifying the predominant psychological consequences of cyberbullying among Indian college students, examining the moderating role of demographic factors like gender and age, and providing a comparative analysis of the psychosocial impact of cyber versus traditional bullying (Baruah et al., 2017). By doing so, it seeks to inform culturally relevant prevention and support strategies.

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2. Related Work:

Current literature on cyberbullying can be categorized as prevalence, psychological impacts, and demographic associations.

2.1 Prevalence and Digital Expansion:

Research indicates a strong association between increase in internet users and cyberbullying. The cyber bullying incidents mainly occurs through various social media sites such as Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, Twitter, WhatsApp, Telegram, Myspace etc. According to (Patchin and Hinduja, 2011) previous researches suggest that from past 10 years there is high increase in internet users or consumers and they are using the internet services for accessing the various social media platforms or websites for messaging, sharing video and images to bully their colleagues or peers (Kaur and Saini, 2023). The results of the survey suggest that majority of the cyber bullying incidents occur through various social media websites or networks. Lapidot-Lefler and Dolev-Cohen (2015) were also having the opinion that due to increase in number of internet users recently have resulted increase in number of cyber bullying incidents among the college students and young individuals. The easy availability and increase in network resources resulted in rapid expansion of online platforms or portals. Finally, it can be concluded that method of detection and prevention of cyber bullying should use in order to handle the cyber bullying incidents properly.

2.2 Psychological Impacts:

The transition from traditional to digital bullying had profound health implication. According to Molluzzo and Lawler (2012) the problems related to cyber bullying is affecting the health of young individuals. Although individual of any age group can be the victim of cyber bullying. Cyber bullying is being considered as the negative side of digital communication in the society. In order measure the extent of cyber bullying the researcher conducted survey on the university students of Pace University. The outcomes suggested that perceived occurrences and extent of cyber bullying have increased in the university students.

2.3 Demographic Factors:

Studies have shown conflicting results regarding demographics. Bakera and Tanrikulua (2010) tried to identify the association between demographic variables such as gender and age with cyber bullying experiences among the Turkish secondary school children. The survey was conducted on 165 secondary students in which 94 students were female and about 71 were males also the age group ranged from 10 to 14 years. The research outcome suggests that there is an association between age and gender on the cyber bullying experiences. Other major finding concludes that students being cyber victim have higher degree of depressive symptoms. However, further research is required to validate these findings within the higher education demographic in India

2.4 The Indian Context:

Extant literature in India is available but it often lacks depth in examining the psychological impact and demographic interactions specific to the population (Savani et al., 2023).

2.5 Research Gap:

This study addresses the lack of comprehensive, empirical research within India that simultaneously assesses a broad spectrum of psychological consequences, rigorously tests their association with key demographics, and directly compares the impact of cyber and

traditional bullying. This multifaceted approach is the novel contribution of the present work (Bansal et al., 2024).

3. Methodology:

The study examines the impact of cyber bullying on psychological behaviors. The present study focused on the psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents, demographic aspects such as gender, age, course, educational qualification, location etc. and identify the impact of traditional bullying and cyber bullying on psychosocial behaviors of college going students in Indian perspective (Achuthan et al. 2022). The psychosocial health issues included distress feelings, depression, anxiety, insomnia, suicidal attempts, low self-worth, social loneliness, self-harm etc.

3.1 Research Design and Sampling: This study utilized a descriptive research design. A sample of 500 respondents was selected from various colleges in India using the convenience sampling technique. This sampling method was chosen due to the accessibility of the student population and time constraints (Gull et al., 2025).

3.2 Instrument and Measures Primary data was collected using a well-structured questionnaire divided into two sections:

1. **Demographics:** Gender, age, course, and location.
2. **Bullying Scale:** Questions assessing the type of bullying (traditional vs. cyber), extent of victimization, and specific psychological consequences (e.g., distress, insomnia, self-harm).

3.3 Reliability and Analysis The instrument demonstrated high internal consistency, with a **Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.91**. Data were analyzed using SPSS and Excel, employing statistical tools including Mean, Standard Deviation, Frequency, Rank/Percentile, and Chi-Square tests to determine associations (Vishwakarma et al., 2025).

3.4 Objective:

1. Psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India.
2. Demographic aspects and psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents.
3. Compare traditional bullying and cyber bullying influence on psychosocial behaviour in Indian perspective.

3.5 Ethical Approval: The study was conducted in adherence to ethical standards for human subject's research (Singh and Singh, 2025). The research protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC).

4. Hypotheses:

1. **H1₀:** There is no significant difference between psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India based on demographic factor gender.
2. **H2₀:** There is no significant difference between psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India based on demographic factor age.
3. **H3₀:** There is no significant difference between psychological behaviour among college students of India based on type of bullying either traditional bullying or cyber bullying.

In order to collect primary data well- structured questionnaire was being developed which consists of questions related to demographic aspects, type of bullying, kind of cyber bullying, extent of cyber bullying, awareness about cyber bullying, psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among the youth specially college going students (Muhammed & Samak, 2025). Although secondary data was taken from government sites, published reports in various journals and medical digests etc. The survey instrument was analysed based on the measures reliability and validity using “Cronbach's Alpha Method”. The calculated value of Cronbach's Alpha was about 0.91 which concludes that there is high internal consistency in the scale being used (Sergeeva and Zheltukhina, 2025). The statistical tools used for analysis were mean, standard deviation, percentage analysis, frequency, Chi-Square test, rank and percentile. Analysis was done using the application software Excel and SPSS.

5. Results:

The gender wise classification of respondents is shown below in the table 1:

Table 1: Gender wise classification

Gender Wise	No. of Respondents	No. of Respondents (%)
Male	250	50%
Female	250	50%
Total	500	100%

The sample size of about 500 respondents was being considered. About 50% college students were female from different degree colleges and other 50% respondents were male college going students.

Table 2: Age wise classification

Age Group	No. of Respondents
18-24	250
25-34	200
35 & above	50
Total	500

About 50% students were from the age group 18-24 years which accounts for about 250 respondents, 40% respondents were between the age group 25-34 years and about 10% college students belong to the age group 35 & above years.

5.1 Traditional and Cyber Bullying:

Table 3: Recently victim of traditional or cyber-Bullying

Type of Bullying	No. of Respondents
Cyber bullying	402
Physical bullying	30
Social bullying	45
Verbal bullying	23
Total	500

When traditional bullying ways are compared with cyber bullying it was found that about 402 respondents which accounts for about 80% approx. of total respondents confirmed that they were victim of cyber bullying incidents and only 20% were being victim of traditional bullying ways such as physical, social and verbal bullying.

5.1 Psychological consequences and cyber bullying incidents:

The psychological consequences after cyber bullying victimization being identified were distress feelings, depression problem, change in behaviour, anxiety level, Insomnia, Suicide attempt, fearfulness, low feelings, social loneliness, academic performance, stress level, self-harm, post-traumatic stress indications, substance abuse, frustration level, increase in anger level, decreased self-esteem and Schizophrenia problem (mental health issue).

Table 4: Psychological consequences and cyber bullying incidents

Cyber-bullying impact on Students	Yes	No
Distress feelings about the bullying	400	100
Depression	320	180
Mood swings	122	378
Increased anxiety level	450	50
Insomnia (Numb problems)	100	400
Suicide attempt or ideation	50	450
Fearfulness	450	50
Self-worth low feelings	320	180
Social loneliness	409	91
Avoiding things that used to enjoy	201	299
Decrease in academic performance	300	200
Self-harm	310	190
Post-traumatic stress indications	122	378
Substance abuse	121	379
Frustration level increases	460	40
Increase in anger level	450	50
Decreased self-esteem	200	300
Schizophrenia problem	10	490

Majority of the respondents about 92% confirmed that frustration level increases after cyber bullying incident. Similarly, about 90% were with opinion that their anger level increased after victimization, 90% confirmed that their anxiety level increased after the incident of cyber bullying. It can be concluded that cyber bullying has very high impact on psychological behaviour of college going students. So in order to reduce the impact of cyber bullying proper awareness programs should be conducted by college management and government.

Table 5: Psychological consequences & cyber bullying incidents Rank & Percentile score

Cyber-bullying Impact on Students	Rank	Percentile
Distress feelings about the bullying	6	70.50%
Depression	7	58.80%
Mood swings	13	23.50%

Increased anxiety level	3	82.29%
Insomnia (Numb problems)	16	11.70%
Suicide attempt or ideation	17	5.80%
Fearfulness	4	82.27%
Self-worth low feelings	7	58.80%
Social loneliness	5	76.40%
Avoiding things that used to enjoy	11	41.10%
Decrease in academic performance	10	47.00%
Self-harm	9	52.90%
Post-traumatic stress indications	13	23.50%
Substance abuse	15	17.60%
Frustration level increases	1	100.00%
Increase in anger level	2	82.30%
Decreased self-esteem	12	35.20%
Schizophrenia problem	18	0.00%

According to the table above with rank & percentile values it can be interpreted that frustration level increases, increase in anger level and increased anxiety level are the major psychological consequences that the students face after cyber bullying victimization.

Table 6: Psychological consequences & traditional bullying incidents

Traditional bullying Impact on Students	Yes	No
Distress feelings about the bullying	388	112
Depression	200	300
Mood swings	100	400
Increased anxiety level	250	250
Insomnia (Numb problems)	90	410
Suicide attempt or ideation	30	470
Fearfulness	400	100
Self-worth low feelings	300	200
Social loneliness	320	180
Avoiding things that used to enjoy	150	350
Decrease in academic performance	221	279
Self-harm	120	380
Post-traumatic stress indications	56	444
Substance abuse	23	477
Frustration level increases	300	200
Increase in anger level	402	98
Decreased self-esteem	250	250
Schizophrenia problem	5	495

Table 7: Psychological consequences & traditional bullying incidents Rank & Percentile score

Traditional bullying Impact on Students	Rank	Percentile
Distress feelings about the bullying	3	88.20%
Depression	10	47.00%
Mood swings	13	29.40%
Increased anxiety level	7	58.80%
Insomnia (Numb problems)	14	23.50%
Suicide attempt or ideation	16	11.70%
Fearfulness	2	94.10%
Self-worth low feelings	5	70.50%
Social loneliness	4	82.30%
Avoiding things that used to enjoy	11	41.10%
Decrease in academic performance	9	52.90%
Self-harm	12	35.20%
Post-traumatic stress indications	15	17.60%
Substance abuse	17	5.80%
Frustration level increases	5	70.50%
Increase in anger level	1	100.00%
Decreased self-esteem	7	58.80%
Schizophrenia problem	18	0.00%

(H3₀) Psychological Behavior & Type of Bullying**Figure 1:** Hypothesis related to psychological behaviour & type of bullying

When comparing cyber bullying with traditional bullying ways it can be concluded that cyber bullying victimization impact are more serious on psychological behaviour as compared to traditional bullying which includes physical, social and verbal which concludes that hypothesis H3₀ is rejected. Although the three major psychological consequences identified after traditional bullying victimization are increase in anger level, fearfulness and distress feelings about the bullying.

5.2 Psychological consequences of cyber bullying and demographic factor gender:

H1₀: There is no significant difference between psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India based on demographic factor gender.

H1_a: There is significant difference between psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India based on demographic factor gender.

To test the above-mentioned hypothesis related to psychological consequences of cyber bullying and demographic factor gender various individual hypotheses related to various consequences as shown below in the table were being framed.

Figure 2: Hypothesis & Sub-Hypotheses (Psychological consequences and demographic factor gender)

Table 8: Hypothesis testing results for psychological consequences of cyber bullying and demographic factor gender

S. No.	Hypothesis	Chi-Square Calculated Value	Chi-Square Tabulated Value	Result	Significant at 5%
H1.1 ₀	There is no significant difference between distress feelings about the bullying & gender	89.10	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.2 ₀	There is no significant difference between depression & gender	177.63	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.3 ₀	There is no significant difference between mood swings & gender	5	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.4 ₀	There is no significant difference between increased anxiety level & gender	56.44	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.5 ₀	There is no significant difference between Insomnia (Numb problems) & gender	1.33	3.84	Accepted	Not Significant
H1.6 ₀	There is no significant difference between suicide attempt or ideation & gender	14.18	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.7 ₀	There is no significant difference between fearfulness & gender	20	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.8 ₀	There is no significant difference between self-worth low feelings & gender	76.8	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.9 ₀	There is no significant difference between social loneliness & gender	185.03	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.10 ₀	There is no significant difference between avoiding things that used to enjoy & gender	8.57	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.11 ₀	There is no significant difference between	1.82	3.84	Accepted	Not Significant

	decrease in academic performance & gender				
H1.12 ₀	There is no significant difference between self-harm & gender	17.54	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.13 ₀	There is no significant difference between post-traumatic stress indications & gender	1.28	3.84	Accepted	Not Significant
H1.14 ₀	There is no significant difference between substance abuse & gender	0.045	3.84	Accepted	Not Significant
H1.15 ₀	There is no significant difference between frustration level increases & gender	53.33	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.16 ₀	There is no significant difference between anger level & gender	6.4	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.17 ₀	There is no significant difference between decreased self-esteem & gender	135.2	3.84	Rejected	Significant
H1.18 ₀	There is no significant difference between Schizophrenia problem & gender	1.18	3.84	Accepted	Not Significant

The null hypotheses testing results suggests that the hypotheses H1.1₀, H1. 2₀, H1.3₀, H1.4₀, H1.6₀, H1.7₀, H1.8₀, H1.9₀, H1.10₀, H1.12₀, H1.15₀, H1.16₀ and H1.17₀ are being rejected as in all cases the calculated Chi-Square value was found to be greater than the tabulated Chi-Square Value. Further it can be concluded that there is association between anger level and gender. Similarly testing results related to other major psychological consequences also suggest that anxiety and frustration level are also significant with demographic factor gender.

5.3 Psychological consequences of cyber bullying and demographic factor age:

H2₀: There is no significant difference between psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India based on demographic factor age.

H2₁: There is significant difference between psychological consequences of cyber bullying incidents among college students of India based on demographic factor age.

Similarly in order to test the above hypothesis various individual hypotheses related to various consequences as shown below in the table were being framed.

Figure 3: Hypothesis & Sub-Hypotheses (Psychological consequences and demographic factor age)

Table 9: Hypothesis testing results for psychological consequences of cyber bullying and demographic factor age

S. No.	Hypothesis	Chi-Square Calculated Value	Chi-Square Tabulated Value	Result	Significant at 5%
H2.1 ₀	There is no significant difference between distress feelings about the bullying & age	4.07	5.99	Accepted	Not Significant
H2.2 ₀	There is no significant difference between depression & age	297.8	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.3 ₀	There is no significant difference between mood swings & age	1041.22	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.4 ₀	There is no significant difference between increased anxiety level & age	155.18	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.5 ₀	There is no significant difference between Insomnia (Numb problems) & age	1208.10	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.6 ₀	There is no significant difference between suicide attempt or ideation & age	4557.37	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.7 ₀	There is no significant difference between fearfulness & age	6.22	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.8 ₀	There is no significant difference between self-worth low feelings & age	67.48	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.9 ₀	There is no significant difference between social loneliness & age	43.21	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.10 ₀	There is no significant difference between avoiding things that used to enjoy & age	542.83	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.11 ₀	There is no significant difference between decrease in academic performance & age	229.02	5.99	Rejected	Significant

H2.12 ₀	There is no significant difference between self-harm & age	791.42	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.13 ₀	There is no significant difference between post-traumatic stress indications & age	2223.65	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.14 ₀	There is no significant difference between substance abuse & age	6087.82	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.15 ₀	There is no significant difference between frustration level increases & age	67.48	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.16 ₀	There is no significant difference between anger level & age	6.98	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.17 ₀	There is no significant difference between decreased self-esteem & age	155.18	5.99	Rejected	Significant
H2.18 ₀	There is no significant difference between Schizophrenia problem & age	29705.66	5.99	Rejected	Significant

The null hypotheses testing outcomes suggests that the hypotheses H2.2₀, H2.3₀, H2.4₀, H2.5₀, H2.6₀, H2.7₀, H2.8₀, H2.9₀, H2.10₀, H2.11₀, H2.12₀, H2.13₀, H2.14₀, H2.15₀, H2.16₀, H2.17₀ and H2.18₀ are being rejected as in all cases the calculated Chi-Square value was found to be greater than the tabulated Chi-Square Value. Further it can be concluded that there is association between anger level and age. Similarly testing results related to other major psychological consequences also suggest that anxiety and frustration level are also significant with demographic factor age. Only the hypothesis H2.1₀ was accepted which concludes that there is no significant difference between distress feelings about the bullying & age.

5.4 Hypothesis Testing (Chi-Square Analysis)

Gender & Psychological Consequences (H1₀)

The analysis rejected the null hypothesis for key indicators. Significant associations were found between gender and:

- Depression $\chi^2 = 177.63$
- Anxiety $\chi^2 = 56.44$
- Anger Level $\chi^2 = 6.40$
- Frustration $\chi^2 = 53.33$

- **Result: H1₀ is Rejected.** Gender significantly influences the psychological impact of cyberbullying.

Age & Psychological Consequences (H2₀)

The analysis rejected the null hypothesis for most consequences, indicating age is a significant differentiator.

- **Exception:** H2.1₀ (Distress feelings) was accepted ($\chi^2 = 4.07 < 5.99$), suggesting distress is universal across age groups.
- **Result:** H2₀ is largely Rejected.

Comparisons (H3₀)

Comparing the data, cyberbullying victims reported higher frequencies of severe psychological outcomes (anxiety, frustration) compared to traditional bullying victims. Thus, H3₀ is rejected²⁶.

6 Discussion

This study highlights a disturbing trend: 80.4% of surveyed students have experienced cyberbullying, a figure significantly higher than traditional bullying forms. This aligns with findings that predicted rising cases due to expanding online opportunities.

Psychological Impact: The most prevalent outcomes were Frustration, Anger, and Anxiety. This contradicts some studies done by (Al Majali et al., 2020) that prioritized depression as the primary outcome, suggesting that for Indian college students, the immediate reaction to digital victimization is highly emotive (anger/frustration) before manifesting as depressive withdrawal. The high ranking of "Fearfulness" (Rank 4) indicates that the anonymity of cyberbullying creates a pervasive sense of threat.

Demographic Nuances: The Chi-square results confirm that gender and age are not neutral variables. The significant association between gender and anxiety/anger implies that males and females may process digital aggression differently. The acceptance of the null hypothesis regarding "Distress" across age groups suggests that while the *reaction* (e.g., anger vs. withdrawal) changes with age, the fundamental feeling of distress remains constant.

Limitations: This study relied on convenience sampling, which may limit generalisability. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data may introduce bias. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference. Future research should employ longitudinal designs, validated clinical scales, and random sampling. Qualitative studies could provide deeper insight into the subjective experience of victims in the Indian cultural context.

7 Conclusion and Recommendations:

The study identifies various psychological consequences after cyber bullying victimization among them the most serious consequences being identified were increases in frustration, anger and anxiety level about 92% students as respondents confirmed that cyber bullying has increased the level of frustration. Similarly, about 90% students confirmed that their anger level increased after victimization and 90% respondents were with the view point that their anxiety level has increased after cyber bullying victimization. Accordingly, the results conclude that there is significant difference between psychological behaviour among college students of India based on type of bullying either traditional bullying or cyber bullying also it can be concluded that there is association between anger level and gender. Similarly, there is

relationship between anxiety level & gender and frustration level & gender as the calculated Chi-Square value is greater than the tabulated Chi-Square value respectively 56.44 and 53.33 at 5% level of significance.

7.1 Recommendations:

1. **Institutional Policy:** Colleges must implement strict anti-cyberbullying policies that extend beyond physical campus boundaries.
2. **Awareness Programs:** Management and government bodies should conduct regular workshops and seminars to educate students on digital etiquette and legal consequences.
3. **Counseling Services:** Dedicated psychological support for digital victimization should be integrated into college health centres.

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